

The Situation, Dilemma and Path Choice of Network Ideological Public Opinion Governance in the New Era

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ABSTRACT : *The Internet has become the main battlefield of ideological struggle. The marketization of network media, network politics, big data technology and network survival have become the new scene of network ideological governance in the new era. At present, there are some difficulties in the governance of network ideology, such as the governance ability needs to be strengthened, the governance concept needs to be improved, the governance means are relatively backward, and the governance system lacks coordination. Therefore, we need to build a governance force from the four aspects of governance concept, governance means, governance ability and governance system to comprehensively enhance the governance efficiency of network ideological public opinion in the new era.*

KEYWORDS : *new era, Internet ideology and public opinion, government*

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Cyberspace has increasingly become the source of public opinion, the distribution center of information dissemination and the forefront of the struggle between infiltration and anti infiltration in the ideological field. It is expanding and reconstructing the contemporary ideological space in an all-round way. In the network public opinion field like micro-blog, WeChat and jitter, the ideological controversy caused by specific social events happens almost every day. Many social trends of thought carry network debate to further ferment, spread and spread through cyberspace, making the ideological tiktok and struggle in cyberspace more obvious [1]. The generation and dissemination of network ideology public opinion have great influence on people's ideology, value judgment and orientation. We should strengthen the governance research on the generation, dissemination and diffusion of network ideology public opinion, and improve the security of mainstream ideology.

I. THE ERA SITUATION OF NETWORK IDEOLOGICAL PUBLIC OPINION GOVERNANCE IN THE NEW ERA

In the new era, with the rapid development and popularization of the Internet, great changes have taken place in the media environment and ecology, and great changes have taken place in the production, circulation and consumption of information.

1.1 The marketization of network media is the economic scene of network ideology and public opinion governance.

Negative externality of network information refers to the negative consequences of network information service institutions in providing network information services in pursuit of maximizing enterprise interests and minimizing costs. They do not treat the poor quality network information, let it spread on the network, pollute the network information space, and cause negative consequences that damage the legitimate rights and interests of others, public interests, social, political and economic order and even the security of cultural information. Under the condition of socialist market economy, media organizations are more regarded as economic organizations than social organizations. The trend of media marketization is accelerating. Many media operate and manage by means of corporatization.

For the majority of ordinary people, Sina, Tencent, Netease, Baidu and other Internet companies have become the main platforms for them to understand information. The development of these Internet enterprises cannot do without the promotion of capital. This will inevitably lead to the demands of commercial or political interests in the network platform information. In order to obtain more click through rate, bind more users for long-term use, many network platforms blindly cater to users, obtain more rewards, and provide users with unrestrained and frequent "what they need" audio and visual content, forming "network culture products", some of which are not only the products of network culture. The covert dissemination of the contents that violate the socialist core values, and even the attack and digestion of China's mainstream ideology, by constantly stimulating the sensitive nerves of the people, can easily lead to the security problems of the mainstream ideology.

1.2 Network politics is the political scene of network ideological public opinion governance

The effectiveness and responsiveness are two dimensions of modern political legitimacy. The governance of network ideology and public opinion needs to respond to real life, realize effective communication between government and Internet users, and will constantly give vitality to political legitimacy. The socialist political system with Chinese characteristics provides a political basis for individual citizens, civil organizations and all social strata to participate in and discuss government affairs. It is possible for individual citizens, civil organizations and all social strata to participate in and discuss government affairs through various channels.

Due to the blessing of the Internet media, the channels of citizens' political participation have become more convenient and diverse. In the new era, citizens are asking more and more questions about public health, environmental protection, the protection of the rights and interests of vulnerable groups, housing security and education equity. Some Internet public opinions trigger Internet ideological public opinions, which puts forward higher requirements for government departments to respond to the demands of Internet users in a timely manner. If we ignore the timely response to the Internet public opinion, the Internet ideological public opinion may continue to intensify.

Through the timely response of the government to the Internet public opinion, the effective communication between the government and Internet users is realized, the effectiveness of social policies is improved and the legitimacy of government governance is consolidated. The governance of Internet ideology and public opinion is not only the need to listen to public opinion and accept social supervision, but also the need to regulate the behavior of Internet users and maintain the order of cyberspace.

1.3 Big data technology is the technical scene of network ideology public opinion management

During the second collective learning of the Political Bureau of the CPC Central Committee in 2017, Xi Jinping stressed that "we need to strengthen learning, understand big data, make good use of big data, enhance the ability of using data to promote all kinds of work, constantly improve the ability to grasp the law of the development of big data, and make big data play a greater role in every work" [2]. The importance of technology to public opinion governance lies not only in the tool attribute of technology, but also in its change and shaping of public opinion governance concept and governance mode. As an important part of social institutions, mass media organizations participate in the construction of social system. Language is born with the function of carrying and transmitting certain ideology, and the development of ideology is also born closely related to language. If ideological discourse only stops at the internal Abstract speculative link and lacks the external specific language expression, it will inevitably fall into the discourse dilemma of "no reason, no way

and no transmission", thus greatly reducing the discourse power of ideology.[8] The construction of ideological discourse power must attach importance to the position construction of discourse communication.

The advantages of big data technology are conducive to improving the effectiveness of network ideological public opinion governance. In the era of big data, for the main body of ideological governance, data is an important basis for making governance decisions. Network ideological public opinion governance should make full use of the information and value contained in data to make accurate decisions on ideological public opinion. The governance subject of ideological public opinion can use big data technology to analyze and compare the changes of public opinion data, timely grasp various demands and suggestions of Internet users, and use the advantages of fast network big data to quickly integrate multiple explosion points of a topic discussion, classify the opinion tendency of topic discussion, and quickly screen out opinion leaders in the dissemination of ideological public opinion.

1.4 Network survival is the social scene of network ideological public opinion governance

Network survival has become a new way of life for people in the new era. As people's field of activity, network media is not only the flow of information, but also the carrier of activities such as sharing, negotiation, compromise, communication and confrontation. The web media such as portal, social media, information aggregation platform, knowledge sharing community and other network media enter people's life scene. The audience realizes information exchange, entertainment, shopping, friends making and chat activities in the network media to meet their own needs. In the era of network, network space can extend and expand human living space with its virtual beyond reality, mutual communication, dynamic openness of system, sharing of massive resources, immediacy of information transmission, diversity of cultural forms, and extending and expanding human living space. In this way, it can effectively release and display human essential power.

The low cost of network use, the digitalization of communication mode and the immediacy of communication form make the communication speed faster and wider, which correspondingly brings weak relationship communication, non homogeneity communication and non direct communication; the uncertainty of communication subject identity, the weakening of communication norms, the instability of communication relationship and the informality of communication language result in the shallowness of communication Trust, short-term volatility, content fragmentation, which leads to the crisis of trust, the absence of emotion, the weakening of responsibility, the weakening of ethics, the lack of meaning [3].

II. The dilemma of network ideological public opinion governance in the new era

The characteristics of the network ideology public opinion are discrete, changeable, complex and interactive, which bring great risks to the network ideology public opinion. The difficulties of governance mainly show that the capacity of governance subject needs to be strengthened, the governance concept needs to be improved, the governance means are relatively lagging behind and the governance system lacks coordination. Due to the lack of effective governance, the network ideological public opinion management has entered the "jungle period" of absence and failure, which highlights the crisis of network ideological public opinion governance.

2.1 The governance ability of network ideology and public opinion needs to be strengthened

Without an excellent network ideology management team, it is difficult to succeed in building a powerful network country. The governance ability of network ideological public opinion is an important representation of the party's ruling ability in the field of network ideology. We must improve the personnel training system of ideological work, and cultivate an ideological management team with both professional technology and high political quality, so as to improve the effectiveness of the governance of network ideological public opinion. As Xi Jinping said, "we need to solve the problem of" ability panic "and become a real expert [4] in the way of modern media novice Duan Xin. For the government departments of network ideology and public opinion governance, their responsibility is to create a healthy and clean network space.

In the face of the vast cyberspace and the increasing number of applications, the objects of management are expanding. Due to the time difference between the improvement of governance ability and the growth rate of network ideological public opinion, the administrators are often absent, helpless and delayed in the crisis of

network ideological public opinion. At present, the lack of governance ability of network ideological public opinion is mainly reflected in the following three aspects: first, the lack of public opinion research and early warning ability. The research and analysis team of network public opinion governance in China is mainly composed of government department staff, few of whom have received professional and systematic technical training. Many managers judge the risk of public opinion only by experience, and do not understand the characteristics of network ideological public opinion. It is difficult to capture the changes of network ideology and public opinion timely and accurately. The second is the lack of the ability to guide and deal with public opinion. Some public opinion management departments do not take scientific and effective measures to solve the problem in the face of ideological public opinion on the Internet, but take such negative means as deleting, blocking, prohibiting search or even cutting off the Internet to conceal and block information, or respond rashly on the basis of insufficient investigation and evidence collection, which are easy to lead to the occurrence of "secondary public opinion". The third is the lack of public opinion monitoring and collection ability. Some public opinion management departments have limited public opinion early warning and monitoring ability. Network ideological public opinion monitoring is still in the state of manual investigation. It is possible to distinguish the authenticity of information and judge the level of risk by experience, which may lead to incomplete and inaccurate grasp of public opinion information. So there is lag and deviation in the ideological network public opinion information collection, the ability to grasp and analyze the network ideological public opinion is insufficient, and the situation after the outbreak of network ideological public opinion is not handled effectively, so as to miss the best opportunity of network public opinion governance.

2.2 The governance concept of network ideology and public opinion needs to be improved

Thought is the guide of action. There are two problems in the current concept of public opinion governance. First, some governance subjects have insufficient understanding of the importance of public opinion governance. In the struggle in the ideological field, we have no room for compromise and concession. We must firmly hold the leadership, management and discourse power of ideological work in our hands. We can't leave it alone at any time, otherwise we will make irreparable historical mistakes [5]. Many governance subjects have the concepts of "almost" and "roughly" and do not fully understand the importance of network ideological public opinion governance for national ideological security. They will not take the initiative to explore the information value behind the network ideological public opinion. As a result, the network ideological public opinion governance still stays in the primary stage of post remediation, and even the management work is often neglected. Public opinion leads the way. When meeting with public opinion, they are used to asking for instructions layer by layer, and often miss the best period of public opinion governance, which leads to the continuous expansion of the influence of network public opinion, and even produces adverse consequences.

On the main battlefield of network ideology, there are still some comrades who prefer to be "enlightened gentlemen" and justify their inaction with "no argument", "no speculation" and "let talk" [6]. On the one hand, they are not willing to take the initiative to set the agenda in the network public discussion and give up the power of network ideology management; on the other hand, in the network ideological public opinion debate, they lack the consciousness and courage to take the initiative, and some mainstream media practitioners have no political position on major principle issues such as ideological public opinion, resulting in a harmonious so-called "harmonious" atmosphere. The encirclement encouraged the spread of wrong ideas and virtually made the socialist mainstream ideology lose a lot of positions.

Second, the concept of emphasizing management over service. Under the influence of traditional management concepts such as "official standard" and "power center", the relevant government departments take "I" as the main body, the "power" as the center, the "management" as the means, and the binary opposition thinking as the main thinking in the process of network ideological public opinion governance. They always regard Internet users as the governance objects, which reflects the distrust of Internet users in thought, cognition and emotion. When it comes to ideological public opinion on the Internet, it rigidly believes that "public opinion is the enemy's", aiming at maintaining political stability rather than solving problems in public opinion.

2.3 The governance means of network ideology and public opinion are relatively backward

Xi Jinping pointed out that online media management and industrial management are far behind the development of the situation. Especially in the face of the rapid growth of users of social media and instant

messaging tools such as wechat and wechat, which spread fast, have great influence, wide coverage and strong social mobilization ability, how to strengthen the construction of network legal system and the guidance of public opinion to ensure the order of network information dissemination, National security and social stability has become a prominent problem in front of us [7].

At present, the governance of network ideology and public opinion relies too much on experience and traditional management means. However, the traditional media management means are far behind the pace of media development, and the relative lag of its governance means is mainly reflected in the following two aspects.

One is the narrowing of public opinion governance means. The government dominated restraining force focuses on the upper limit of the evolution of Internet public opinion, that is, controlling public opinion should not be too hot, or emotions should not be too negative, but almost does not pay attention to the lower limit, that is, it does not worry that there are no objections or important events are ignored. Even for some major sensitive news will be directly "forbidden" [8]. Using administrative power and technical means to forcibly encircle and suppress ideological public opinion on the Internet, closing the comment function of public opinion website, forbidding the release of sensitive words related to public opinion, or using online reviewers to dive and post to dilute negative comments to physically cool ideological public opinion on the Internet. This simple governance method is effective in the era of traditional media, but it is not effective For the new era of network ideological public opinion governance will only make the public opinion governance departments fall into a passive situation and lose the initiative of network ideological public opinion governance. Second, the attitude of public opinion governance is rigid. In the face of complex and turbulent Internet ideological public opinion, government departments and their officials, as the main body of response, sincerely face the questions and demands of Internet users, explain the causes and consequences of the event in detail and meet the public's right to know, are the important factors affecting the governance of Internet ideological public opinion. However, in reality, some government departments and their officials in response to the network public opinion discourse anomie phenomenon occurs frequently, official full, difficult to meet the needs of Internet users, easy to cause the spread of public opinion.

2.4 Lack of coordination of network ideology and public opinion governance system

At present, the governance of network ideology and public opinion in China is mainly government governance, which does not coordinate and mobilize the active participation of other subjects, leading to "governance failure" [9]. This lack of coordination is mainly manifested in two aspects: one is the lack of internal linkage. At present, China's party and government organs at all levels have not established an authoritative and unified ideological network public opinion management organization. The propaganda departments of Party committees at all levels, the Internet management departments and the information technology departments lack tacit understanding. When the network ideological public opinion occurs, there is often a lack of unified command. As a result, in the process of network ideological public opinion governance, some governance subjects shirk responsibility Even among the upper and lower levels of the government system, there will be "flexible" implementation, resulting in blind spots and vacuum areas in the governance of network public opinion, or multiple governance, disorderly governance and independent governance. Second, the external cooperation is not enough. Some public opinion management departments are still keen on the traditional way of administrative control, ignoring the cooperation with operators, network platforms, information technology experts and other external forces, resulting in improper response to the public opinion crisis.

III. The path choice of network ideological public opinion governance in the new era

The goal of network ideological public opinion governance is to consolidate the guiding position of Marxism in the ideological field, and consolidate the common ideological foundation of the whole Party and the people. The realization of governance objectives is inseparable from the renewal of governance concepts, the enhancement of governance capacity, the broadening of governance means and the Integrating of governance system..

3.1 Establish the concept of public opinion governance community

The emergence and development of network ideological public opinion are often formed under the joint efforts of the real society and network society, domestic and foreign factors, individuals and organizations. Therefore,

the governance of network ideological public opinion needs to establish the concept of governance community. The reason why community has become an ideal network model is that it can solve the problems of general single network. Can solve the problem, or solve the cost is smaller, lower risk, with higher internal efficiency [10]. Due to the fragmentation of power and responsibility in the traditional public opinion management, it is difficult for the public opinion governance subject to achieve the goal of public opinion governance alone, and it needs to cooperate with other subjects to form a common action. In view of the dilemma of collective action among governance subjects, the best solution to overcome the obstacles of collective action is to build a governance community.

Public opinion governance community means that social organizations and the general public will become the common subject of public opinion governance, share the responsibility of social governance with the party and the government, and share the results of public opinion governance. The party and the government should jump out of the traditional social control thinking and accept the objective fact that they only play a role as a scheduling parameter. In addition to directly participating in the governance process, they should also establish a real partnership with other actors.

3.2 Improve the ability of public opinion management

The ability of network ideology public opinion governance is the embodiment of the national governance ability in the network space. At present, Chinese society should focus on improving the ability of two aspects. First, strengthen the ability of network public opinion to manage according to law. Xi Jinping pointed out: "the Internet is not outside the law." [11] The governance of network ideology public opinion is not only related to the vital interests of Internet users, but also related to the stability and long-term stability of the state power. To purify the network public opinion ecology, we must promote the construction of the rule of law in cyberspace. We should promote the network according to law, run the network according to law and surf the Internet according to law, and ensure the healthy operation of network behavior on the track of rule of law. As in the real space, the network space should not only promote and encourage the free expression of the subject of network behavior, but also maintain the proper discourse boundary, and follow the principles of personal rights protection and the healthy development of the network.

To promote the construction of the rule of law in cyberspace, we must manage the bad information of the network, clarify the bottom line of network behavior, the red line of network space, and the high-pressure line of illegal and illegal network, which is the inevitable choice to purify the network public opinion field. We should promote the ecological governance of network public opinion with the rule of law thinking, fill up the short board of the network space legalization construction as soon as possible, and create a good legal atmosphere and legal guarantee for the rule of law for the network and the network according to law. We should strengthen online legislation, make competent departments, website platforms and netizens have laws, rules and regulations to follow, and follow the rules. We should actively promote the orderly and standardized operation of the network in accordance with the law.

Second, strengthen the ability of network public opinion technology governance. Technology determines the communication power and influence. The network ideology public opinion management technology should keep pace with the times, conform to the development trend of network technology, actively absorb new achievements of network technology. Big data, as a new technology and strategy, has the advantages of management technology such as immediate blocking, dynamic monitoring and big data analysis. The technical trend of network ideology public opinion governance is the necessity of the new era. To ask. Although the talent team in ideology field has good ideological theoretical literacy, it is relatively unfamiliar with big data technology.

The core of big data technology is quantification and prediction. To grasp the law of network ideological public opinion, it means to use big data technology to mine valuable information from massive data for quantitative representation, shift the focus from data collection to in-depth study and judgment of public opinion, and find out the sensitive and high-risk areas prone to network public opinion crisis. Big data can perceive the "where" and "what kind of risk" of network ideology [12]. With the development of cyberspace, the ideological security risk gradually extends from the real life field to the network virtual field. Big data technology can monitor

complex variables in the network ideology space in real time. By analyzing multiple heterogeneous data, big data can locate the missing security information and associate single point of abnormal behavior, so as to find clues that endanger the network ideology security and "trace back to the source" of network security threats.

Due to the huge amount of information of network ideological public opinion, it is difficult to collect and process network public opinion only by manual screening. It is necessary to use big data technology for information screening, use big data technology for social semantic analysis, build network ideological public opinion index and public opinion index, and then form network public opinion monitoring system. Based on a variety of public opinion cases, we use big data technology to establish multi-dimensional public opinion indicators with high degree of visualization, covering quantitative content such as Internet users' occupation data, regional data and age data, and including qualitative content such as emotional change, ideological tendency, opinion expression and social influence, so as to form an identification system combining quantitative indicators and qualitative indicators .

3.3 Improve the means of public opinion governance

Comrade Xi Jinping clearly pointed out in the nineteen major reports: "we should attach great importance to the construction and innovation of means of communication, and enhance the dissemination power, guidance, influence and credibility of news media. We will strengthen the construction of Internet content, establish a comprehensive network governance system and create a clear network space. " [13]

First, we should build an open and transparent channel for public opinion information. Ideological governance is a complex and systematic work. In the process of the evolution of network public opinion, the blocked and blocked channels of communication and the concealment of effective information will aggravate speculation and stress, and cause rumors, rumors and gossip and the gossip obtained from informal channels to flourish. The smooth expression channels will play a similar role of "safety valve", and play a role of "safety valve" To relieve bad mood and maintain social stability. The government should broaden the channels of freedom of expression, establish a standardized and orderly participation mechanism to meet the demands of political participation of the majority of Internet users. Media should actively set up issues on hot and focused issues of social concern, and actively build platform channels for interest diversity demands and expression of diversified opinions of all levels, create convection channels for their dialogue and consultation, so that opinions and opinions of all walks of life can be communicated through the network platform built by media, and mutual understanding can be enhanced to promote social integration.

Second, strengthen the emotional communication in public opinion governance. The generation and dissemination of network ideological public opinion often include both emotional factors and interest factors. Therefore, when taking measures to govern network ideological public opinion, we should give consideration to both reason and reason, and use the communication and persuasion mode of "moving with emotion" and "enlightening with reason" to promote the return of network public opinion from disorder to order. When channeling Internet public opinion, we should not confront or debate with netizens. Instead, we should treat netizens' different needs with tolerance, and conduct benign communication and consultation with netizens with a tolerant and pluralistic attitude, so as to achieve mutual understanding, trust and understanding. In addition, because the behavior of netizens is often dominated by emotion rather than rationality, and those comments published from an authoritative and higher-level perspective will make netizens have a kind of psychological distance, and instinctively reject the objective and rational views and ideas they advocate and flaunt, especially those communication contents with the nature of preaching and indoctrination. Therefore, only by intervening in it with equal status and giving netizens care and love can we really move netizens' emotional hearts and ultimately achieve the purpose of guiding Internet public opinion behavior according to the situation.

3.4 Integrating public opinion management system

Xi Jinping stressed in the 2018 National Conference on network security and informatization: "to improve the ability of comprehensive network governance, we should form a comprehensive governance grid Bureau, [14], which integrates Party committee leadership, government management, corporate accountability, social supervision, netizens self-discipline, and so on. Departments at all levels in charge of modern media

management, information content management and network behavior supervision must refine the division of responsibilities, strengthen cooperation, establish a communication and coordination mechanism among Internet information departments, communication management departments and public security organs, and formulate and improve emergency response plans for major emergencies on the Internet. We should build a governance system led by the government, with multi-agent and multi-level participation, give full play to their respective effects, and achieve collaborative governance. Strengthening the synergy of public opinion governance system is reflected in the following four aspects.

One is to strengthen the relationship of responsibility coordination and co governance between the network ideological governance departments and other party and government departments. In order to change the situation that the departments in charge of network ideology are fighting alone, the leading group of network ideology work with propaganda, public security, politics and law, education, economy and information and other key departments as members can be set up under the leadership of the Party committee and the government in charge and coordinated by the Department of network information, so as to carry out public opinion consultation on major events and important nodes, so as to realize resource sharing and unification The first action is to provide organizational guarantee for the effective governance of network ideological public opinion.

The second is to strengthen the relationship of information sharing and collaborative governance between network ideological governance departments and Internet enterprises. Internet enterprises are important members of the collaborative governance community. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen the cooperation between the governance departments and Internet enterprises, urge Internet enterprises to break the enterprise and industrial barriers, innovate network security governance technology, strengthen the audit of network communication content, resolutely put an end to the ideological public opinion that may lead to the network, consciously assume the responsibility of network security risk prevention and control, and do not worry about it We should improve their ability to fulfill their social and public responsibilities.

The third is to strengthen the relationship of education cooperation and co governance between network ideological governance departments and Internet users. The majority of Internet users are not only the beneficiaries of network security, but also the participants and builders of the ecological governance of network public opinion. On the one hand, the network ideological governance department should carry out network security knowledge education for the majority of Internet users to enhance their awareness of network security; to enhance their concept of network rule of law, the majority of Internet users should strictly restrict their own network behavior and protect their own network environment On the other hand, the majority of Internet users should actively resist and expose the negative opinions on the Internet, and become the guardians of the Internet public opinion ecology.

Fourth, strengthen the cooperative governance relationship between the network ideological governance departments and the network opinion leaders. Many people never think independently, and all choose from the options offered by the elite. In the public opinion field of the Internet world, there are many network opinion leaders, who have strong influence and authority, can influence the views of Internet users to a certain extent and influence the trend of network ideology public opinion. Therefore, general secretary Xi Jinping stressed: "we should strengthen and improve the work of the representative personages in the new media, establish regular channels of contact, and strengthen online interaction and offline communication, so that they can show positive energy in purifying cyberspace and promoting the theme. Strengthening cooperation with network opinion leaders will help unite and strive for the majority of Internet users, so that the ideological governance of the network can receive double the effect of half the effort. "

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